

IMPROVING TOURISM OPPORTUNITIES AND PROSPECTS

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Annotation: The rapid development of market relations, their penetration into the economy, and their impact on the occupied population and all segments of the population. Market relations require new thinking from the population, and the formation of new sectors of the economy requires an increase in its share in GDP. The transition from one economic system to a new economic system affects the standard of living of the population. This is because one of the most important social policies pursued in the country's economy is to ensure employment and improve living standards. The article analyzes important aspects of the formation of the domestic and international tourism market, the growth of employment, and income.

Key words: tourism markets, tourism services, tourism marketing, tourism enterprises, tourism management.

The socio-economic life of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the living standards of the population are changing rapidly. Special attention in the field of tourism services remains an important sector in the development of market relations. The development of tourism services will further improve the income and living standards of the population.

We know that services in the tourism market are geographically divided into domestic and international tourism. Today, pilgrimage tourism, medical tourism and ecotourism are also developing. In particular, international tourism has developed rapidly in our country over the past decade. One of the factors negatively affecting the rapid development of the tourism system in the country is the market of tourist services, ie the national tourism market is not in demand, which in turn allows the tourism industry to develop in areas with large tourist resources. limits. In particular, the current state of development of tourism services, the analysis of indicators determining the future of the industry, the study of economic and organizational factors in the formation of the tourism industry, improving the quality of tourism services, ensuring the competitiveness of national tourism enterprises and national tourism. shows the need for excellent scientific research, which will lay the foundation for the growth of foreign demand for its products. This requires finding ways to

organize and develop the tourism market. Therefore, the market of services in the field of tourism has a special place. Because tourism, as one of the best-developed sectors of the global network today, has a positive impact on the development of interpersonal, cultural, social and political relations at the international level.

In fact, the fact that our country has sufficient opportunities in the field of tourism and is not inferior to any foreign country is the main source of many successes in this area. The President noted that despite the huge potential, they are not used enough, “Only 18 out of 206 thermal and mineral springs are used in the country. For example, the water temperature of Arashan Lakes, located on the Kamchik Pass, is 36 degrees Celsius in winter and summer, which is not inferior to foreign resorts. Alternatively, sanatoriums can be established in Chimbay, Karaozak and Takhtakor around thermal springs with a temperature of 40-70 degrees. The potential of 122 museums in the country is not used to attract tourists. They contain more than 2.5 million items, 112,000 of which are unique to world history and culture.”

With this in mind, it is necessary to carry out a number of measures to develop national and international tourism markets and tourism marketing in our country that meet modern requirements. Tourism marketing and services are unevenly developed among the countries of the world, which is determined by their geographical location, cultural heritage, historical sites and the level of socio-economic development. Uzbekistan's tourism potential is notable for its sacred sites, beautiful nature and historical monuments. The world's tourism industry is recovering as pandemic restrictions are gradually eased. In the first quarter of this year, 610,000 foreign tourists came to our country, or more than twice as much as in the same period last year. However, the formation of the needs of the population, the emergence of international economic integration, the formation and development of the service sector. Marketing in the field of tourism is based on the development of more effective tourist services and improving the quality of tourism products, as well as the organization and management of tourism enterprises to sell them in order to generate revenue, taking into account the ongoing processes in the global tourism market. The need to accelerate the implementation of these tasks means ways to develop modern and quality marketing services and set reasonable prices for services in today's travel agencies. It has a travel agency and needs to be in constant contact with potential customers. Travel agencies also need to develop an optimal pricing policy and use a “price creation” strategy in line with the specifics of the

travel agency. Therefore, it is necessary to organize marketing services in tourism enterprises with qualified staff, and they should be engaged in strategies to improve the performance of the enterprise, to form the image of the tourism enterprise through management and marketing research.

The most developed areas of international tourism services are the countries of Western Europe, which account for more than 75% of the international tourism market and about 60% of foreign exchange earnings. About 20 percent is in the United States, and less than 10 percent is in Asia, Africa and Australia. One of the main reasons for the development of tourism markets is that in the post-World War II years, the recovery of the economy through the introduction of international tourism in Western European countries was a priority. Realizing this at the time, businessmen and entrepreneurs saw in this field of international tourism to spend less money and make more profit. That is why today in Western Europe, the income from international tourism is a significant part of their total income.

The development of tourism management and marketing will depend on the functioning of the tourism market. The descriptions of the various destinations offered by tourism enterprises reflect the essence of the tourism market. First of all, the tourist market is a place where transactions in tourism products take place. However, such trade is not limited to one place.

Khiva ranks first in the number of objects that can be seen by international and domestic tourists. It has 310 facilities, followed by Bukhara with 221 facilities, Tashkent with 144 facilities and Samarkand with 118 facilities. To improve this work, many private tourism companies have been established. Many of them joined trade unions to coordinate their work and cooperate with each other. These organizations create the necessary conditions for their members to operate freely.

Therefore, the development of key services in the national and international tourism markets is important. Tourism services play an important role in improving the living standards and employment of the population. Therefore, tourism will increase the necessary foreign exchange earnings for the country's treasury now and in the future, provide employment and, on this basis, improve its living standards.

The existence of economic and political stability in Uzbekistan shows that there are opportunities for rapid development of this sector. In fact, one of the issues recognized by the world community is becoming one of the leading sectors in the field of tourism services, as well as the fact that the tourism

market is developing steadily. Tourism marketing shapes the tourism market through a tourism service or product.

In conclusion, in tourism management and marketing, services produced in tourism as a tourism product consist of a set of different services. This will determine the role of national and international tourism markets in the sustainable development of the tourism industry.

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